

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the development trends and characteristics of the use of artificial intelligence (AI) within the framework of the national project of the digital economy network in Uzbekistan. The advantages of this area of economic activity compared to the use of other advanced technologies are considered. It focuses on the characteristics of the third wave of business process transformation related to flexible business processes, which use AI to process big data in real time instead of following a predetermined sequence of steps. allows to fundamentally change the business.

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In the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4022 of 21.11.2018 "On measures to further modernize the digital infrastructure for the purpose of developing the digital economy" bodies and other organizations are gradually introducing electronic commerce systems for the exchange of electronic documents and services to individuals and legal entities. At the same time, it is said that the analysis of the actual situation in the field shows that the implemented software documents are scattered as a result of the non-existence of a single information-technological platform that provides integration into the centralized information system. In this, the

development of sectors such as: "Regulation of the digital environment"; "Personnel for the digital economy" and "Information infrastructure"; "Information security"; "Digital technologies"; "Digital public administration" plays an important role.

The challenges of bringing these critical networks to life will certainly lead to the development of the Human and Machine: Business in the Age of Artificial Intelligence process.

According to Wikipedia's widely accepted definition, "artificial intelligence (AI; Artificial Intelligence, AI) is (1) the science and technology of creating intelligent machines, especially intelligent computer programs; (2) traditional

intelligent systems the ability to perform creative functions considered human competence. According to HSE experts, by 2025 the size of the artificial intelligence market will grow 150 times compared to 2016 and reach \$59.7 billion. By 2020, AI will reach 2.3 million creates jobs; by 2022, 20% of non-traditional workers will rely on AI; by 2025, 85% of customer interactions will be driven by AI; by 2030, global GDP 15.7 trillion. The main impact of the use of AI will be obtained by optimizing business processes and expanding the possibilities of automation and robotization of manual labor; reshaping the global labor market and changing educational processes in favor of personalization and development of conceptual thinking; exclusion of subjectivity and irrationality in decision-making [10]. There are two directions of AI development: (1) bringing specialized AI systems closer to human capabilities and solving problems related to their integration by human nature; (2) creating artificial intelligence, which represents the integration of already created AI systems into a single system capable of solving human problems [2, 11]. Fields of application of AI: automatic translation; text recognition; intelligent information security systems; receive business information; get information; speech recognition; recognition of visual images; understand and analyze natural language texts; robotics; expert systems; image analysis and more. Recently, there has been an impressive achievement in the field of development and especially in the field of application of artificial intelligence based on the use of neural networks. Great results have been achieved in solving problems such as speech, image and face recognition. These technologies are based

on rough copying of the human brain and do not always give the expected results. The task of science is to understand how AI works. Technologies often begin to work before we understand all the details of their operation. Without such an understanding, various phenomena will inevitably occur. Nuclear power (Fukushima and Chernobyl) is an example of such a potential negative impact. The same can happen if you don't have a thorough understanding of how AI works. The main problem in AI theory is classical mathematics from the point of view, the task of building neural networks is to understand why neural networks work, despite the fact that the number of observations (training examples) is several orders of magnitude less than the number of specified parameters, but nevertheless, the network works in practice. We don't yet have a theoretical understanding of why the network works. Although this should not prevent us from implementing these technologies on a large scale. The main task of scientists is to learn how AI technologies work as quickly as possible. To bring artificial intelligence to a new level of development and to achieve predictable and reliable results, it is necessary to create a new AI theory or significantly improve it. The decisive word here must remain in mathematics, because it is the "language of the universe" [5, 6, 7]. Scientific research and implementation of artificial intelligence show that companies that use new AI capabilities can achieve technological breakthroughs, tangible results and competitive advantage. AI not only allows for significant modernization of many technological and social processes, making them more efficient (increasing labor productivity and expanding human

capabilities), it changes the nature of work, fundamentally reorganizes management processes and imposes a number of new requirements. At the same time, changing the nature of human-machine interaction.

With the rapid development of AI technologies and the widespread use of applications based on it, businesses are often asked "how many people will lose their jobs due to AI?" questions like For example, according to a survey conducted by the Edelman AI think tank supported by the World Economic Forum (WEF), 91% of executives and 84% of ordinary citizens believe that the arrival of artificial intelligence will herald a new technological revolution. At the same time, the participants of both focus groups seriously fear the consequences of the introduction of AI for society, business and the state. Respondents cited a number of possible problems - from smart toys that invade the child's personal space, to the deterioration of the living conditions of the poor and the loss of human intellectual capacity [3]. Kay Firth-Butterfield, head of the WEF's AI and Machine Learning Program, said: "The research shows that businesses and governments need to take a holistic view of the many challenges facing AI and take appropriate action. should take measures because of the possible negative consequences. The emergence of AI may negate all the benefits of these technologies. The world community should be aware of the risk factors associated with such profound changes and artificial intelligence must prepare conditions that benefit all people. Artificial intelligence affects not the number of jobs, but their content. All this sets new tasks in expanding business competencies and preparing people's minds for radical

changes [1, 8]. Analyzing the possibilities of artificial intelligence, researchers have identified new areas of its application, primarily in business began to search in connection with the improvement of their processes. The use of AI in this field makes it possible to make business processes flexible and flexible, abandon traditional pipelines and move to the idea of integrating advanced AI systems and people. This approach allows for a radical change. machine-human interaction, forming integrated teams of robots and humans. Such teams are able to quickly process large amounts of data during production operations, learn new information and adapt to constantly changing conditions. These AI capabilities allow companies to redesign their business processes, significantly increase efficiency, and reduce costs. Thus, one of the main areas of development and implementation of artificial intelligence in industry is the reengineering of business processes. Another direction in the development and implementation of artificial intelligence is when machines do what they do best (repetitive, monotonous tasks with large amounts of data processing), and humans do what they do best. filling and expanding their capabilities (working with uncertain information, drawing conclusions in complex situations, making decisions in conditions of high level of uncertainty, creativity, etc.). This direction is called the third wave of business transformation. Such a symbiosis of man and machine imposes new requirements on the qualification of an enterprise employee [9]. The employee should be able to: formulate questions for an intelligent agent at different levels of abstraction; effective cooperation with an intelligent agent in

achieving set goals; train intelligent agents in new technological skills and learn yourself; improving the interaction model (interface) with an intelligent agent; joint decision-making with AI under conditions of increased uncertainty; looking for new ways to improve business processes to increase their efficiency.

The idea that artificial intelligence will "take over the world" and exclude the

presence of a person is not correct, and it should be replaced by a new perspective that does not exclude the presence of a person in the workplace, but rather expands his possibilities. Collaborating with AI to improve human productivity, work and solve problems that were previously considered impossible. In conclusion, Artificial Intelligence is necessary for every aspect of our lives.

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